

THE LEVEL OF COMPLIANCE OF TEENAGE MOTHERS TO MATERNAL CARE FROM THE SELECTED BARANGAY HEALTH CENTERS IN MARIKINA CITY: BASIS FOR HEALTH TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

Compliance in maternal care is crucial for fetal health and preventing teratogens during pregnancy. While satisfaction is a key factor influencing compliance. Adolescent health remains a global health concern, and an issue targeted to be addressed by the SDGs. This study aimed to determine the level of compliance and satisfaction with maternal care given to teenagers in Marikina City namely Barangay Malanday and Barangay Tumana. This quantitative study utilized purposive sampling to collect data. The study was carried out with a total of 36 teenage mothers as respondents from the said both barangays. Results revealed that the youngest mother in the study was fourteen years old, and the youngest mother respondent during pregnancy was thirteen years old (13) and was only in Grade 6. Most of the mothers visited the health center for prenatal (86%) and immunization of the mothers (83%) and their level of satisfaction with receiving maternal care is noted to be highly satisfied (weighted mean of 1.75). The result also showed that the level of compliance of teenagers receiving maternal care from the health centers was slightly compliant (weighted mean of 2.64). Furthermore, the researchers discovered that there was no significant relationship between the level of satisfaction and level of compliance as assessed by the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City. The researchers composed a proposed health teaching for teenage pregnant/mothers, barangay health workers, and the parents, this aims to improve teenagers' compliance with health center visits.

Keywords: *Compliance, Satisfaction, Teenage pregnant/mother, Maternal Care*

INTRODUCTION

Health of women throughout pregnancy, childbirth, and the postpartum period is referred to as maternal health. To ensure that women and their unborn children achieve their maximum potential for health and wellbeing, each stage should be pleasant. Despite significant advancement over the past 20 years, 295, 000 women died during or after pregnancy and childbirth in 2017, this amount is just too high. In addition to indirect factors including anemia, malaria, and heart disease, the most frequent direct causes of maternal injury and death are excessive blood loss, infection, high blood pressure, botched abortion, and obstructed labor (World Health Organization [WHO], 2019). Thus, the effort of every professional to give care to the mother and unborn child is vital and needs more effort in order for the mother and child to have a safe delivery and to avoid morbidity and mortality.

Maternal morbidity and mortality remain a major global problem in developing and underdeveloped countries. Various international interventions have been implemented over the last 50 years, but they basically use the same objectives and indicators. This review traces the evolution of maternal and child health programs based on key global guidelines, from the 1978 Declaration on Primary Health Care to the Millennium and Sustainable Development Goals and relates the approaches they have generated to the Philippine experience. Maternal Mortality Ratio (MMR) is still increasing and yet becomes global health issue. Low Middle-Income Countries in the Southeast Asia region are greatly affected by the high rate of MMR. A lot of countries in the Southeast Asia didn't still reach the Sustainable Development Goals (Herwansyah et al., 2022).

According to Nisperos (2022) despite adherence to recommended goals and programs, health outcomes have not improved significantly. New strategies are said to offer new and innovative ways of doing things, but they basically suffer from the same old assumptions. This means that governments have limited resources and must use all available means to support interventions. Despite the current socio-economic climate shaped by neo-liberal and conservative policies, there continues to be a preference for low-cost, measurable programs that provide a minimum of basic services.

The Philippines faces a high Maternal Mortality rate, despite implanting various ways to use Maternal Health Care programs to provide Services in order to lessen it. Utilizing the maternity care services that are accessible might assist decrease maternal morbidity and death and close the gap between community adolescent mothers' need for and usage of such services (Cagayan et al., 2022). The maternal mortality and morbidity in the Luzon, Philippines has factors that affects teenage pregnant mothers to utilize the maternal services such as non availability of skilled health worker and financial status. It also identifies that the factors that deter the patient to receive maternal care services should be eliminated. By eliminating these barriers will help the local community to improve the Services given to teenage pregnancy and give them a chance to utilize the maternal health Service to lessen the maternal mortality. Less usage of medical services by women who give birth at home could result in more frequent atypical symptoms throughout the postpartum period. These symptoms may lead to the maternal mortality rate in the Philippines (Yamashita et al., 2017).

As cited in Hadian et al. (2019) a systematic review study in Iran 2017 showed that adolescents are at higher risk of complications in pregnancy and childbirth, which may interfere with Iran's national development goals (reduction of maternal mortality and morbidity). Adolescents face additional negative individual and societal responses to preterm birth and may therefore have less freedom to access services compared to older mothers (Hackett et al., 2019). Exavery et al. (2013 as cited in Hackett et al., 2019) states that in Tanzania it had reported that women who had unplanned pregnancies tend to be hesitant to visit antenatal care (ANC) this resonates with the experiences of many adolescents in our study who expressed embarrassment at an unexpected early pregnancy and subsequent reluctance to attend ANC.

Pregnant teenagers had factors that affected their everyday life, self esteem, and lack of budget. The maternal mortality and morbidity in Nigeria is increasing because of the lack of utilizing the Maternal Health Service (MHS) of pregnant teenage mothers. In the study of Odetola and Mekwunyei (2020) further discussed that the maternal health services had been proven that using it as a tool to provide maternal care to teenage pregnant mothers was very effective to lessen the rate of maternal mortality and morbidity. Encouraging the pregnant teenage mother to attend and use the MHS will help them and will lessen the mate

According to Sewpaul et al. (2021), there was evidence of a differing connection between the pregnant teens and the health staff. Adolescents experienced mistreatment and discrimination from the medical staff, which deterred them from visiting antenatal clinic A number of variables affect the multifaceted idea of maternal satisfaction. Maternal satisfaction with the delivery process is used to gauge how well the services offered are able to live up to customers' expectations. Additionally, happy customers are more likely to use the facility again in the future and tell their friends and family about it (Gejea et al., 2020). Satisfaction in patients gives them the urge to attend their appointments, comply with their medications, give the appropriate immunization to their babies or in general, it encourages them to receive all the care that they need during and after pregnancy for themselves and for their neonates. A key indicator of quality in healthcare systems is typically thought to be the degree of satisfaction with maternal healthcare services (Kidane et al., 2022) Promotion of good health and counseling and rehabilitation came up as two themes. Teenage first-time mothers wanted to learn more about important topics like family planning, breastfeeding, immunization, and self- and newborn care (Namutebi et al., 2021)

The municipal health officer of Mabini, Compostela Valley Dr. Gesim states that "because of the prenatal check-ups and the presence of the facilities, we have no more maternal deaths here in Mabini in 2017" (WHO, 2018, News section). The barangay health teams could now send pregnant women to the health center for high-quality maternal health services closest to home, in addition to the building, supplies, and equipment, which has been a great benefit of this project.

According to Islam and Masud (2018) Bangladesh's level of compliance with the WHO's recommended level of maternal care use during pregnancy, delivery, and the postnatal period is unsatisfactory. Bangladesh's government and non-governmental organizations have placed a great deal of focus on safe motherhood policies and programs, but the

nation is still a long way from having all women receive the required maternity care. Meanwhile, in the context of our health centers it is noted by Health Director Dr. Eric Tayag to ABS-CBN News that all health centers in the nation still need to strengthen leadership and governance, health finance, health information, availability of drugs, vaccinations, technology, human resource, and delivery services (Chanco, 2019). This shows that there are still problems specifically in the local health centers here in our country that still need to be assessed and be solved.

The researchers chose this study in order to evaluate how compliant are the teenage mothers in the selected barangay in Marikina City with regards to the maternal care services given to them. It is a fact that age is a big factor affecting the capability of taking responsibilities and obligations whether at home, work, school or even in their own health.

Research Questions

Given the increasing maternal mortality rate in the Philippines and the unique challenges faced by pregnant teenagers, this study aims to explore the level of compliance of maternal care given to teenagers by a selected Health center in Marikina City. The researchers also seek to find answer to the following questions:

1. What is the Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Age when you got pregnant
 - 1.3 Educational Background
2. What is the maternal care needed in visiting selected health centers in Marikina City?
3. What is the level of satisfaction of the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City?
4. What is the level of compliance of teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of satisfaction of the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers and level of compliance of teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City?
6. What measures can be proposed to assist the development aid in developing Health teaching?

METHODOLOGY

This quantitative study used a correlational approach to determine the compliance and satisfaction of teenage mothers to maternal care offered by the selected health centers in Marikina city. This measured how well they complied with and how satisfied they were with the maternal care they received both during and after pregnancy. The sampling method that was utilized by the researcher is total enumeration sampling in which the researcher decides to look at the complete population that has a specific set of characteristics. The researcher's target population were teenage mothers from the

selected Barangay Health Centers in Marikina City. Based on Marikina City Health Office, Barangay Tumana and Malanday were among the top 3 barangays which had the highest number of adolescent pregnancies and births in Marikina City. The researchers only accessed 25 teenage mothers from Barangay Tumana and 11 from Barangay Malanday with a total of 36 respondents from both barangay

The inclusion criteria were as follows:

- Pregnant teenagers (ages 13 -17) receiving prenatal care at Malanday Health Center and Tumana Health Center within the 3 years starting 2019.
- Teenage mothers (already given birth) receiving postnatal care at Malanday Health Center and Tumana Health Center within the 3 years starting 2019.
- Has an appointment and undergoes a follow-up check-up visit during and after pregnancy only in Barangay Malanday at Barangay Tumana Health Center in Marikina City

The exclusion criteria were as follows:

- Mothers ages 18 years old and above
- Pregnant mothers ages 18 years old and above
- Follow-up check-up and visits outside Barangay Tumana and Barangay Malanday Health Center Marikina City
- Pregnant teenagers who only took prenatal care in Barangay Tumana and Barangay Malanday in Marikina City
- Teenage parents who only took postnatal care in Barangay Tumana and Barangay Malanday in Marikina City.
- Teenage parents who were only going to Barangay Tumana and Barangay Malanday Health center for neonatal care after giving birth.
- Mothers who were in the intrapartum stage of pregnancy

The researcher was able to make a 36 self-made questionnaire in Likert scale of five choices. The questionnaire made by the researchers was validated by the experts, specifically an Obstetrician who had expert experiences in handling maternal services for legal aged mothers or maternal teenagers. Additionally, the researchers also asked for the validation of experts in the field of public health, specifically registered nurses who were in the public health sector, who knew the perspective of different services offered in a local health clinic. To test the reliability of the questionnaire, the researchers utilized Cronbach Alpha and were able to obtain a value of 0.82 interpreted as good internal consistency. The survey contained four parts in total where the part I contained the informed consent. Part II included the demographic profile of the respondents. Part III contained a Likert scale questionnaire to assess the level of satisfaction of the teenage mothers. For part IV this contained the level of compliance that was measured by the service quality of the health center rendered to the respondents. The answers that the

researchers obtained from the survey would be the data to be utilized in the next steps of the research.

The following arbitrary scale was used to interpret the data gathered:

Scale	Range	Verbal Interpretations	Adjectival Description for Level of Satisfaction	Adjectival Description for Level of Compliance
1	1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Agree	Highly Satisfied	Highly Compliant
2	1.80 – 2.59	Agree	Satisfied	Compliant
3	2.60 – 3.39	Neutral	Slightly Satisfied	Slightly Compliant
4	3.40 – 4.19	Disagree	Less Satisfied	Less Compliant
5	4.20 – 5.00	Strongly Disagree	Not Satisfied	Not Compliant

Figure 1. Arbitrary Scale

The researchers employed the following statistical treatment to interpret the data gathered such as the Frequency and Percentage, Weighted mean and Pearson r product correlation.

With constant communication with the Marikina City Health Office the researcher was able to obtain the approval from the City Health Office. With Marikina City Health Office recommendation to the two barangays the researchers was able to obtain data with the assistance of the Barangay Health Workers who helped the researchers to conduct a face to face survey.

RESULTS

Research Question #1. What is the Demographic profiles of the respondents in terms of:

Table 1.1 Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20	1	2.78
19	8	22.22
	486	

18	11	30.56
17	11	30.56
16	2	5.56
15	1	2.78
14	2	5.56
Total	36	100.00

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age. Notice that the most frequent age of the respondents were ages 17-18 years old with 30.56%. The oldest respondent was only twenty years old only. Youngest mother was fourteen (14) years old.

Table 2. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age during pregnancy

Age	Frequency	Percentage
17	16	44.44
16	9	25.00
15	4	11.11
14	6	16.67
13	1	2.78
Total	36	100.00

Table 2 shows the age of the respondents during pregnancy. Most common age of the mother respondents was seventeen (17) with frequency of 16. The youngest age was thirteen (13) years old.

Table 3. Demographic profile of the respondents in terms of educational background

Educational Background	Frequency	Percentage
Grade 12	1	2.78
Grade 11	9	25.00
Grade 10	3	8.33
Grade 9	9	25.00

Grade 8	7	19.44
Grade 7	6	16.67
Grade 6	1	2.78
Total	36	100.00

Table 3 revealed the educational background of the mother respondents. Noticed that most of them were in Grade 9 and Grade 11 with a frequency of eleven (11). Youngest was in Grade 6.

Research Question #2. What is the maternal care needed for visiting selected health centers in Marikina City?

Table 4. Maternal Care needed for Visiting selected Health centers in Marikina City

Maternal Care	Frequency	Percentage
Pre-natal	30	83.00
Post-natal	24	67.00
Immunization for mother	31	86.00
Immunization for baby	29	81.00
Family Planning	22	61.00
Health Counseling	21	58.00
Health Education	26	72.00

**Multiple response; n=36*

Table 4 shows the maternal care needed for visiting selected health centers in Marikina City. Observed that the frequency is more than the total number of the respondents since the visiting mother respondents have more than one reason for visiting the health center. Observes that in their barangay, 21 adolescent moms have a lower frequency of receiving health counselling and family planning. Most of them visit for pre-natal and immunization of the mother.

Research Question #3. What is the level of satisfaction of teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City?

Table 5. The Level of Satisfaction of the Teenagers Receiving Maternal Care from the selected Health Centers in Marikina City

Level of Satisfaction	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. The services that I need were provided for me.	1.78	Strongly Agree
2. The service for my health problems were managed appropriately.	1.94	Agree
3. First time services were performed right for me.	1.83	Agree
4. They fulfilled the needed service for me and performed at the right time.	1.86	Agree
5. Error-free services were maintained for patients like me.	1.64	Strongly Agree
6. Health care services were well explained by the service provider.	1.72	Strongly Agree
7. Services were prompt for patients like me.	1.67	Strongly Agree
8. Health service providers were courteous and approachable.	1.78	Strongly Agree
9. My questions and queries were attended to by the health workers.	1.64	Strongly Agree
10. My concerns were handled professionally by the health workers.	1.64	Strongly Agree
11. I felt safe and comfortable during the consultation or health check-up.	1.67	Strongly Agree
12. My health is dealt with by the health care workers with tenderness, love and care.	1.72	Strongly Agree
13. I performed the exercises recommended by my doctor or healthcare provider.	1.75	Strongly Agree
14. My needs were understood by the health care workers.	1.83	Agree
15. Modern equipment was utilized for my consultation.	1.83	Agree
16. The facility maintains a clean environment for patients like me.	1.67	Strongly Agree

17. The health care workers were neat and well-groomed while attending patients like me.	1.64	Strongly Agree
18. Services are properly advertised through visual aids for patients like me.	1.92	Agree
Over-all Weighted Mean	1.75	Strongly Agree (Highly Satisfied)

Table 5 shows the level of satisfaction of the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City. The highest computed weighted mean of 1.64 was found in 4 statements numbers 5,9,10 and 20 “Error free services were maintained for patients like me, my questions and queries were attended to by the health workers, my concerns were handled professionally by the health workers and the health care workers were neat and well-groomed while attending patients like with verbal interpretation “strongly agree”. This implied that the health care workers were careful in giving service to make sure that findings were free from errors, handling their patients professionally.

While the lowest computed weighted mean of 1.94 was found in the statement number 2, “The service for my health problems were managed appropriately” verbally interpreted agree. This meant that most of the respondents agreed that their health problems were managed appropriately. The over-all weighted mean was 1.75 with verbal interpretation strongly agree. Using the arbitrary scale, it is equivalent to being highly satisfied. This implied that the level of satisfaction of the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City was highly satisfied. Health care workers professionally handled their patients and gave prompt service.

As per Kidane et al. (2022) a key indicator of quality in healthcare systems is typically thought to be the degree of satisfaction with maternal healthcare services. To determine how satisfied moms were with their care during delivery.

Research Question # 4. What is the level of compliance of teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City?

Table 6. The Level of Compliance of the Teenagers Receiving Maternal Care from the selected Health Centers in Marikina City.

Level of Compliance	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation
1. I know that the purpose prenatal/postnatal is to avoid complications during pregnancy.	1.58	Strongly Agree
2. I've had trouble remembering when to attend my prenatal/postnatal appointments.	2.53	Agree

3. I did not attend my prenatal/postnatal appointment because I feel I do not need it.	3.64	Disagree
4. My prenatal/postnatal appointments are not helping me.	4.17	Disagree
5. My physical problems keep me from attending my prenatal/postnatal appointments.	3.50	Disagree
6. I think that any of my postnatal/prenatal consultations were giving me a good effect.	1.56	Strongly Agree
7. I know all the dates of my prenatal/postnatal appointments because I am very eager to do it for my pregnancy.	1.83	Agree
8. I think that I need all of my prenatal/postnatal appointments.	1.64	Strongly Agree
9. In the past 6 months, I have had difficulty getting a new prenatal/postnatal appointment.	3.75	Disagree
10. I often missed attending my prenatal/postnatal appointment.	3.56	Disagree
11. I have forgotten attending any of my prenatal/postnatal appointments within the past few months.	3.25	Neutral
12. The cost of my prenatal/postnatal check-up concerns me.	3.81	Disagree
13. I took the needed test such as CBC, blood sugar, urinalysis etc. as it is needed in my check up during my pregnancy and advised by my Doctor.	1.89	Agree
14. I am following my doctor's recommended diet.	2.22	Agree
15. I am taking my vitamins and medicines that are prescribed by my doctor.	1.92	Agree
16. I attended my required prenatal/postnatal check-ups.	2.03	Agree
17. I performed the exercises recommended by my doctor or healthcare provider.	2.81	Neutral
18. I am taking the vaccines and immunizations advised by my Doctor. (Ex. Tetanus Toxoid)	1.81	Agree
Over-all Weighted Mean	2.64	Neutral (Slightly Compliant)

Table 6 shows the level of compliance of teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City. The highest computed weighted mean of 1.56 was found in statement number 6, "I think that any of my postnatal/prenatal consultations were giving me a good effect" with verbal interpretation of strongly agree.

This implied that the teenagers who received maternal care acknowledged that the post-natal and prenatal consultations gave them good effect. This validated the lowest computed weighted mean of 4.17 in statement number 4, that “prenatal/postnatal appointments are not helping me”. This implied that their schedule postnatal/prenatal were important in order to make sure that the babies were alive and healthy in their womb. The over-all weighted mean was 2.64 with verbal interpretation of neutral. Based on the arbitrary scale, neutral means slightly compliant. This implied that the level of compliance of teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City were slightly compliant.

According to Hadian et al. (2019) adolescent pregnancy is a public health concern that affects mothers, their children, and the wider community. Complications of pregnancy and childbirth remain a leading cause of mortality and morbidity among adolescent girls worldwide and can be influenced by lifestyle choices. Teenage pregnancy rates are on the rise worldwide and recent changes in family planning policies in Iran are estimated to increase teenage pregnancies in the near future. Current research suggests that teenagers be provided accurate information on pregnant women's health habits and related factors.

In the study of Odetola and Mekwunyei (2020) further discussed that the Maternal health services has been proven that using it as a tool to provide Maternal care to Teenage pregnant mothers is very effective to lessen the rate of maternal mortality and morbidity. Encouraging the pregnant teenage mother to attend and use the Maternal Health Service (MHS) will help them and will lessen the Maternal mortality and morbidity rate, especially in the undeveloped countries.

Research Question #5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of satisfaction of the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers and level of compliance of teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City?

Table 7. Test of Relationship between the Level of Satisfaction and Level of Compliance of the Teenagers receiving Maternal Care from the selected Health Centers in Marikina City

Pearson r Value	Sig-Value	Decision	Verbal Interpretation
0.201	0.240	Accept	Not Significant

Table 7 shows the relationship between the level of satisfaction and level of compliance of the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City. The computed Pearson r value was 0.201 with significant value 0.240 which was greater than the level of significance 0.05, therefore the hypothesis was accepted. There was no significant relationship between the level of satisfaction and level of compliance as assessed by the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City.

This implied that even the health care workers professionally handled their patients and gave prompt service was rated highly satisfied. Although the level of compliance assessment of the teenagers who are receiving maternal care was slightly compliant.

As cited in Hadian et al. (2019) a systematic review study in Iran (2017) showed that adolescents are at higher risk of complications in pregnancy and childbirth, which may interfere with Iran's national development goals (reduction of maternal mortality and morbidity). Consequently, the development of an adolescent-specific health practice improvement strategy can have a significant role in achieving national development goals. Given the high risk of teenage pregnancy, maternal and neonatal complications and the positive impact of health practices on health status and reduction of adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes, health practices in pregnancy should be encouraged, especially in adolescents.

According to the study of Namutebi et al. (2021) promotion of good health and counseling and rehabilitation came up as two themes. Teenage first-time mothers wanted to learn more about important topics like family planning, breastfeeding, immunization, and self- and newborn care. They pointed out that health professionals must keep an eye on their vital signs because doing so helps with disease prevention and treatment as well as early diagnosis of complications. Others said that health professionals were crucial in mediating between them and their estranged parents and in establishing linkages between them and community organizations that might offer them counseling and life skills. This shows that the role of health care workers were vital for the first time teenage mothers in where they stand as their guide in place of their parents. Thus, health care workers must give extra attention to take care of the teenage mothers in order to answer their worries and questions.

Research Question #6. What measures can be proposed to assist the development aid in the development of health teaching?

Proposal	Expected Result
<p>For the maternal teenagers / young parents</p> <p>Teach the teenage pregnant/mother about the importance of pre and postnatal care and the teratogenic factors that can affect the fetus/baby.</p> <p>Give information on why compliance to consultation at the Health Center are important for their baby/fetus and themselves.</p> <p>Include the importance of healthy lifestyle choices such as exercise, walking and</p>	<p>Teenage pregnant who learned information about prenatal care, will be able to attend future appointments/consultation.</p> <p>The number of pregnant teenagers' compliance to their follow up checkup in the health center increases.</p> <p>Numbers of maternal teenagers will be less anxious and more prepared for giving</p>

<p>yoga to prepare their perineal muscles for giving birth and to promote good circulation, and as well as to lessen the stress they are experiencing such as anxiety and overthinking.</p> <p>Inform the maternal teenagers and young parents about the affordable nutritious food.</p> <p>Encourage the target population to adhere and continuously learn more about breastfeeding and its importance.</p> <p>Instruct the importance and encourage both target populations to take the medications and vitamins prescribed for them and their babies.</p> <p>Encourage both target populations in adhering with regards to immunizations needed for them and their babies and its importance.</p> <p>Encourage both target populations to attend parenting sessions even before or after giving birth to inform them the importance of good parenting strategies, safety precautions and techniques.</p>	<p>birth and the young parents who newly give birth will do it for faster wound healing.</p> <p>The teenage parents and maternal teenagers identify healthy and nutritious food that will benefit both the mother and the baby that will also fit on their budget.</p> <p>The teenage parents will be more adherent to breastfeeding their babies. While the maternal teenagers will verbalize the importance of breastfeeding after giving birth.</p> <p>Both target populations will take advantage of the free services including medications and vitamins and regularly take it for them and the baby.</p> <p>Both target populations will attend and willingly participate on their immunization schedule whether for the mother or the baby.</p> <p>Both target populations will be able to demonstrate basic safe techniques in taking care of their babies and verbalize good parenting strategies.</p>
<p>For the Barangay Health Workers</p> <p>Encourage Barangay Health Worker to establish better rapport in serving the target population to understand more about their concern.</p> <p>Encourage the BHWs to have a focus assessment especially for maternal teenagers and young parents.</p> <p>Inform the importance of continuous monitoring for maternal teenagers and</p>	<p>The target population openly verbalizes their concerns and needs to the Barangay health worker.</p> <p>The BHWs will have one on one assessment for each target population and thoroughly address their independent needs.</p> <p>The Barangay Health Center will have 3 days in a week separated check-ups</p>

<p>young parents and suggest a more frequent and accessible operation schedule for check-ups.</p> <p>Motivate the BHWs in doing home visit especially those who are remotely located to the Barangay Health Center to encourage the maternal teenagers and new young parents to comply and set up an schedule in the Barangay health center for close monitoring.</p> <p>Instruct the BHWs to emphasize free services and medications the Barangay Health Center readily provide for the target population.</p>	<p>accessible and exclusive for the maternal teenagers and young parents.</p> <p>The BHWs will visit the target population in the remote area for close monitoring, and encourage those who are noncompliant in attending the regular schedule needed for them and their babies.</p> <p>The target population will be less anxious with regards to their financial concern in acquiring health services including medications and will be more aware of the free services given by their Barangay health center.</p>
<p>For the Parents</p> <p>Encourage parents to guide their child in doing good parenting techniques, safety precautions and techniques.</p> <p>Instruct parents to encourage their child to adhere to the health appointments needed for both the mother and the baby.</p> <p>Instruct parents to monitor their child's lifestyle with regards to food, vitamins and nutritional diet as well as the exercise needed in avoiding maternal and child complications.</p> <p>Assist parents to recall proper breastfeeding techniques and its importance so they can assist their child in doing it.</p>	<p>The target population will be easily monitored at home while doing safety precautions in parenting strategies and techniques.</p> <p>The target population will be guided accordingly about their appointments as their parents are assisting them in their schedule and avoid missed appointments.</p> <p>The target population will be assisted by their parents in doing lifestyle modifications and acquire proper diet and vitamin intake to avoid maternal and child complications.</p> <p>The target population will be assisted by their parents in breastfeeding and avoid the danger of misdoing the procedure.</p>

Figure 2. Proposed Health Teaching Output

Figure 3 shows the researcher's proposal for health teaching. The researchers propose to teach the teenage pregnant/ mother about the importance of prenatal and post-natal care and the teratogenic factors that can affect the baby in their womb. This will help them be informed and able to attend the scheduled consultation.

Secondly, the researchers would like to give information about why they need the compliance of the schedule consultation at the health center and its health benefit not only for the teenage mother but also for the babies. This may lead to an increase of the number of pregnancies that will go to the health center for follow-up. Furthermore, Pregnant teenagers cooperation with health advice can help barangay health workers and other healthcare professionals manage systemic, comprehensive, and innovative methods for experiencing a successful pregnancy and delivery of the baby.

According to the study of Namutebi et al. (2021) promotion of good health and counseling and rehabilitation came up as two themes. Teenage first-time mothers wanted to learn more about important topics like family planning, breastfeeding, immunization, and self- and newborn care. They pointed out that health professionals must keep an eye on their vital signs because by doing so helps with disease prevention and treatment as well as early diagnosis of complications. Others said that health professionals were crucial in mediating between them and their estranged parents and in establishing linkages between them and community organizations that may offer them counseling and life skills. This shows that the role of health care workers are vital for the first time teenage mothers in which they will stand as their guide in place of their parents. Thus, health care workers must give extra attention to take care of the teenage mothers in order to answer their worries and questions.

Overall, this shows the total need of collaboration between the 3 including the target population (maternal teenagers and young parents), barangay health workers and the parents to empower the participation and compliance of the target population in acquiring their health needs especially during and after pregnancy. All the proposed health teaching by the researchers will be a big help for service modification to be able to guide the target population from the Barangay Health Center or even within their home in getting use of their everyday lifestyle now that they are about to have a child or already have one. Parents' guidance from within the home and the acceptance from the Barangay Health Center from a very little concern up to addressing their major needs will make the target population feel important and accepted, and by doing so, they will feel comfortable in attending their consultation as they know they have a special space from those people who they might be willing to get help from.

DISCUSSION

The summary of findings was drawn based on the data gathered:

1. In table 1 the most frequent age of the respondents were ages 17-18 years old with 30.56%.
2. In table 2 most of the age of the mother respondents was seventeen (17) years old with frequency of 16.
3. In table 3 most of them became pregnant when they were in Grade 9 and Grade 11.
4. Table 4 shows that the visiting mother respondents had more than one reason for visiting the health center. Most of them visited for prenatal and immunization of the mother.

5. Table 5 shows the level of satisfaction of the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City. The overall weighted mean was 1.75 with verbal interpretation of strongly agreed. Using the arbitrary scale, it was equivalent to being highly satisfied.
6. Table 6 shows the level of compliance of teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City. The overall weighted mean was 2.64 with verbal interpretation of neutral. Based on the arbitrary scale, neutral meant slightly compliant. This implied that the level of compliance of teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City were slightly compliant.
7. Table 7 shows the test of relationship between the level of satisfaction and level of compliance of the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City. The computed Pearson r value was 0.201 with significant value 0.240 which was greater than the level of significance 0.05, therefore the hypothesis was accepted. There was no significant relationship between the level of satisfaction and level of compliance as assessed by the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City.
8. Figure 3 shows the researchers proposal for health teaching and the expected outcome that teenage pregnant/mothers will be able to do for future consultations/appointments and hence, increase their compliance in the selected health centers in Marikina City. It also shows the health teaching proposal for the Barangay Health Workers that it needed to be modified and by doing so, would be able to encourage the young parents and maternal teenagers to adhere in their appointments with regards to their health and their children. Lastly, was the proposed health teaching for the young parents and maternal teenagers' parents that would be able to assist and guide them even within their homes.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn based on the summary of findings:

1. The oldest respondent was only twenty years old only. Youngest mother was fourteen years old. The youngest mother respondents during pregnancy is thirteen (13) years old who was only in Grade 6.
2. Most of them visited the health center for prenatal and immunization of the mother.
3. The level of satisfaction of the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City was highly satisfactory. Health care workers professionally handled their patients and gave prompt service.
4. The level of compliance of teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City were slightly compliant.
5. There was no significant relationship between the level of satisfaction and level of compliance as assessed by the teenagers receiving maternal care from the selected health centers in Marikina City.

Recommendations

This study showed that compliance and satisfaction had no significance. The result showed that the respondents were highly satisfied with the healthcare workers, who worked professionally and the respondents' compliance to maternal care service were slightly compliant. Based on the survey results, the researchers offer the following recommendations:

1. To guide the students to comprehend the importance of teenage mother's compliance and satisfaction with maternal care as well as its quality.
2. To the teenagers to be aware and ready to be compliant into taking care of themselves and the baby if they become pregnant in the future.
3. Pregnant mothers to be motivated when it comes to their prenatal or postnatal appointments. And to know the importance of compliance to their appointments.
4. To the parents to be well informed and encourage their children when it comes to compliance. Search the consequences of non-compliance so that they will set as an example to their children to be compliant to their prenatal and postnatal appointments
5. To the health centers, may this be a foundation for health education as well as an assessment of whether teenage mothers receiving care are satisfied with the services they are receiving, also whether they are sufficient and appropriate for them. It will also be enable them to encourage teenager mothers who are missing appointments and/or who have not visited a health center since they first became pregnant.
6. To the Health Policy Maker, may they use as their guide as they work with the school to develop a plan in creating an adolescent center connected to the local government unit (LGU) where they can go if they become pregnant and have concerns about their health or the health of their unborn children, even without the supervision of their parents.
7. To the School Administrator, may this be a foundation on how they will cope with the students in their school that having pregnant teenagers, on how they will treat them and on how they will give solution for those teenage mother who can't manage their time to go to school and do certain task that will compromise their pregnancy. Professional development sessions for teachers should be held, giving them the chance to be trained to be knowledgeable and better able to discuss with the students the key components of the curriculum. With the high school to increase teacher and parental awareness about the teenage pregnancy and their compliance for their health.
8. To the Local Government Unit, may this be their basis for further health teaching for young individuals not only for women. All government organizations and tools are mandated to find and execute workable interventions, such as comprehensive sexuality education, educational and career possibilities for youth, and health promotion through media and communications, in order not only to combat teenage pregnancies but also implement the strategies on compliance about their health and babied.

9. To the future researcher, to expand the findings, more studies should be done on a bigger sample of this population. To be able to know the depth of the compliance of maternal teenagers in different locale and on bigger population.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

First and foremost, the researchers conduct the survey and let the respondents do a voluntary participation wherein they are free to withdraw or give their answers in the surveys at any point in time. The researchers provided an informed consent where the participants will be able to know the purpose, the benefits, the risk and the reason behind the study before they agree or decline to join. The researchers maintained their anonymity, personal identifiable data is not collected aside from the demographic data we needed for the research. Confidentiality is also utilized wherein the researchers kept all the data and information that was collected for academic purposes only and hidden from everyone else aside from the researchers. The researchers also apply the ethical principle of nonmaleficence where we do not implicate any potential harm, physically, emotionally, socially and psychologically. Lastly, and the result of communication wherein the researchers tried their best to make the research plagiarism free, to avoid research misconduct and accurately represent the result.

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